

Appendix A: Questionnaire used in KMar Crowd Study

Demographic questions

1. What is your role at the KMar? (Operational colleague, Team leader, Management, Analyst, IT-employee, other).
2. How did you learn about the *KMar-Crowd*? (E-mail from *KMar-Crowd*, in the briefing, told about by a colleague, mail forwarded by a colleague)

Way of working

All questions used a five-point Likert scale, unless indicated.

1. It is clear to me what I have to do on the platform.
2. I liked this way of being involved in the development of S-Sys/V-Sys.
3. I expect that this way of working results in a product (S-Sys/V-Sys) which we can use.
4. I expect the input I have submitted will actually be used.
5. I was enthusiastic to think about S-Sys/V-Sys in this way.
6. The IT department will just ignore the ideas submitted on this platform.
7. Do you have anything to add about the way-of-working tested on this platform? (open question)

Gamification system

All questions used a five-point Likert scale, unless indicated.

1. The fact that I was able to earn badges resulted in me visiting the platform more.

2. I thought the badges system was childish.
3. I would have been less active on the platform if I was not able to receive badges.
4. I thought the badges system was fair.
5. What I had to do to earn a badge was realistic.
6. I wanted to visit the *KMar-Crowd* more often, but I did not have the time.
7. Do you have anything to add regarding the badge system? (open question)

Final questions

1. Do you have any other comment? (open question)
2. Is it okay if the researcher contacts you to discuss your answers given? (Yes/no).